

ANALYSIS OF ACCURACY OF CUBIC SPLINE FUNCTIONS USING ANALYTIC FUNCTIONS

Zaynidinov Hakimjon

H.Z Professor, Department of Artificial Intelligences,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Azimov Bunyod

B.A Associate professor,
Department of Artificial Intelligences,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Kuchkarov Muslim

M.K Associate professor,
Department of Artificial Intelligences,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abduganiev Mukhriddin

M.A Doctoral student,
Department of Information Technologies,
Andijan State University,
Andijan, Uzbekistan.

Abstract: After many scientific studies in the world, we can say that the use of spline functions in working with digital signals is widely used and good results are achieved. Nowadays, there are many ways to wish digital signals. Examples of them include Lagrange and Newton interpolation methods, spline function, Fourier series and exponential function approximation methods, orthogonal methods for solving systems of linear equations, discrete wavelet transforms and a number of other

interpolation methods. During the research work, cubic Bezier spline function and Hermite spline function were selected for equal intervals. This article describes in detail the process of interpolation of functions to approximate local cubic spline functions to given analytic functions.

Key words: piecewise polynomial methods, local spline functions, local Hermite spline function, interpolation process, cubic spline for equal intervals, mathematical models, analytical functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly developing information and communication technologies in the world, it is becoming important to develop high-performance, efficient computing methods for recovering detected signals, using digital processing algorithms and finding optimal solutions. In particular, it is an important mathematical tool in the creation of digital signal processing algorithms due to the small number of calculations in the construction of local spline functions, the high level of accuracy, the flexibility of digital processing algorithms, optimal differential and extremal properties, and the simplicity of parameter calculation [6], [13].

II. METHODS

Below we present the construction of several local spline functions. So, let's consider the construction of the Bezier cubic spline function, which is one of the piecewise polynomials:

In the general case, the formula for constructing an n-level Bezier spline function for points f_i is given (1):

$$B_3(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n B_{i,n}(x)f_i \quad (1),$$

here, $b_{i,n}(x)$ are called Bernstein polynomials and are calculated as follows(2):

$$b_{i,n}(x) = C_i^n x^i (1-x)^{n-i} \quad (2),$$

and C_i^n are called Binomial coefficients. C_i^n coefficients are calculated based on the formula (3).

$$C_i^n = \frac{n!}{i!(n-i)!} \quad (3),$$

here, $n! - n$ means factorial.

So, by combining formulas (2) and (3), as a result, we get the formula (4) that determines Bernstein polynomials of degree n :

$$B_{i,n}(x) = \frac{n!}{i!(n-i)!} x^i (1-x)^{n-i} \quad (4),$$

For example, we calculate cubic Bernstein polynomials using formulas (4):

$$B_{0,3}(x) = \frac{3!}{(3-0)!} x^0 (1-x)^{3-0} = (1-x)^3 \quad (5),$$

$$B_{1,3}(x) = \frac{3!}{(3-1)!} x^1 (1-x)^{3-1} = 3x(1-x)^2 \quad (6),$$

$$B_{2,3}(x) = \frac{3!}{2!(3-2)!} x^2 (1-x)^{3-2} = 3x^2(1-x) \quad (7),$$

$$B_{3,3}(x) = \frac{3!}{3!} x^3 (1-x)^{3-3} = x^3 \quad (8).$$

Cubic Bernstein polynomials in the interval $[0:1]$ have the following form (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. View of cubic Bernstein polynomials.

When $n=3$ in formula (1), using (5)-(8) we create $B_3(x)$ Bezier spline (9).

$$B_3(x) = f_0 B_{0,3}(x) + f_1 B_{1,3}(x) + f_2 B_{2,3}(x) + f_3 B_{3,3}(x) = f_0(1-x)^3 + f_1 3x(1-x)^2 + f_2 3x^2(1-x) + f_3 x^3. \quad (9).$$

Below we consider the construction of the local cubic Hermite spline method. We know that $f_i, i = 0, N$ is the general view of the n -degree polynomial connected with nodes (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Overview of f_i nodes.

We look for the polynomial to be constructed in the following form:

$$g(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N a_i x^i \Rightarrow$$

$$g(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3 + \dots + a_Nx^N. \tag{10}$$

During interpolation:

$$g(x_i) = f_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N.$$

We develop an interpolating polynomial equal to the function and its derivatives up to p -order at $N+1$ points.

For this we define the following:

$$g(x_i) = f_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N.$$

$$g^{(1)}(x_i) = f_i^{(1)}, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N.$$

$$g^{(p)}(x_i) = f_i^{(p)}, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N. \tag{11}$$

We have $(p+1)$ and $(N+1)$ common constraints for (10) and (11). Using the formulas (10) and (11) above, we form a general polynomial of degree $(p+1)(N+1)-1$ (the number of constraints must be equal to the number of coefficients of the unknowns in the interpolating polynomial).

$$g(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{(p+1)(N+1)-1} a_i x^i. \quad (12)$$

The Hermite interpolation spline function is constructed in 3 steps:

1. Determining the interpolating polynomial;
2. Determination of restrictions;
3. Finding unknown coefficients, $a_i, i = 0, (p + 1)(N + 1) - 1$.

Let us construct a function for the interval $[0, 1]$ and a local interpolating cubic Hermite spline function passing through two nodes passing through its first derivative.

	x	f	$f^{(1)}$
x_0	0	f_0	$f_0^{(1)}$
x_1	+1	f_1	$f_1^{(1)}$

where, $p=1$ and $N+1=2$.

Step 1. We set the boundary condition $(1+1)(2)=4$. According to step 3, we determine the third-order (cubic) interpolating polynomials, taking into account $(p + 1)(N + 1) - 1$.

$$g(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3$$

$$g^{(1)}(x) = a_1 + 2a_2x + 3a_3x^2$$

Step 2. We set limits based on the following conditions..

$$g(0) = f_0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad a_0 = f_0$$

$$g(1) = f_1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3 = f_1$$

$$g^{(1)}(0) = f_0^{(1)} \quad \Rightarrow \quad a_1 = f_0^{(1)}$$

$$g^{(1)}(1) = f_1^{(1)} \quad \Rightarrow \quad a_1 + 2a_2 + 3a_3 = f_1^{(1)}$$

Step 3. We determine unknown coefficients using a matrix.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_0 \\ f_1 \\ f_0^{(1)} \\ f_1^{(1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Using formula (13), we find unknown coefficients a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 (13).

$$a_0 = f_0,$$

$$a_1 = f_0^{(1)},$$

$$a_2 = 3f_1 - 3f_0 - f_1^{(1)} - 2f_0^{(1)}$$

$$a_3 = -2f_1 + 2f_0 + f_0^{(1)} + f_1^{(1)}$$

Given unknown coefficients (11) to the formula $(p+1)(N+1)-1$, $g(x)$ can be described as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} g(x) &= S_3(x) \\ &= f_0 + f_0^{(1)}x + (3f_1 - 3f_0 - f_1^{(1)} - 2f_0^{(1)})x^2 \\ &\quad + (-2f_1 + 2f_0 + f_0^{(1)} + f_1^{(1)})x^3 = \\ &= f_0 + f_0^{(1)}x + 3f_1x^2 - 3f_0x^2 - f_1^{(1)}x^2 - 2f_0^{(1)}x^2 - 2f_1x^3 + 2f_0x^3 + f_0^{(1)}x^3 \\ &\quad + f_1^{(1)}x^3 = \\ &= f_0(2x^3 - 3x^2 + 1) + f_1(-2x^3 + 3x^2) + f_0^{(1)}(x^3 - 2x^2 + x) + \\ &\quad f_1^{(1)}(x^3 - x^2). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$S_3(x)$ can be expressed in general form as follows:

$$S_3(x) = f_0\alpha_0(t) + f_1\alpha_1(t) + f_0^{(1)}\beta_0(t) + f_1^{(1)}\beta_1(t), \quad (15)$$

where, $\alpha_i(x), \beta_i(x)$ $i = 0,1$ basis functions third degree polynomials can be expressed as:

$$\alpha_0(t) = 2t^3 - 3t^2 + 1 \quad \beta_0(t) = t^3 - 2t^2 + t$$

$$\alpha_1(t) = -2t^3 + 3t^2 \quad \beta_1(t) = t^3 - t^2$$

Calculate $f_0^{(1)}$ and $f_1^{(1)}$ in formula (15), $f_0^{(1)} = h_i f'_i$, $f_1^{(1)} = h_i f'_{i+1}$ can be expressed as $\alpha_i(t), \beta_i(t)$ $i = 0,1$ basis functions can be expressed in a simpler case as follows. That is, we replace $f_i(t)$, $i = 1,2,3,4$:

$$\varphi_1(t) = (1-t)^2(1+2t), \quad \varphi_3(t) = t(1-t)^2,$$

$$\varphi_2(t) = t^2(3-2t), \quad \varphi_4(t) = -t^2(1-t).$$

Considering the calculation of the steps for each interval with $h_i = f(x_{i+1}) - f(x_i)$, the cubic Hermite spline-function will have the following form (16):

$$S_3(x) = \varphi_1(t)f_i(x) + \varphi_2(t)f_{i+1}(x) + \varphi_3(t)h_i f'_i(x) + \varphi_4(t)h_i f'_{i+1}(x) \quad (16)$$

here,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_1(t) &= (1-t)^2(1+2t), & \varphi_3(t) &= t(1-t)^2, \\ \varphi_2(t) &= t^2(3-2t), & \varphi_4(t) &= -t^2(1-t), \\ h_i &= f(x_{i+1}) - f(x_i). \end{aligned}$$

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION.

The local interpolation cubic Hermite spline-function graph constructed above and the Bezier cubic spline-function graph depending on the nodes were compared. We compare the approximation of these two local cubic splines with the given function $f(x)$:

Fig. 3. Results of interpolating the function $f(x) = 3^x$ with two cubic splines

Fig. 4. Results of interpolating the function $f(x) = 3^{-x}$ with two cubic splines

IV. CONCLUSIONS.

We can be seen from Figures 3, 4 that the graph of the spline function $S_3(x)$ better approximates the graph of the function $f(x)$ than the graph of the mathematical model of the spline $B_3(x)$. Considering the high accuracy and simplicity of the construction of the local Hermite spline mathematical model in the digital processing of signals, its use in the digital processing of biomedical, geophysical and other signals can lead to high efficiency.

REFERENCES

- [1] Zavyalov Yu.S., Kvasov B.I., Miroshnichenko V.L. Spline function methods. Moscow: Nauka, 1980. - 352 p.
- [2] Zayniddinov Kh.N. Methods and means of signal processing in piecewise polynomial bases. 2015, Tashkent. - pp. 29-40. Xakimjon, Z., & Bunyod, A. (2019). Biomedical signals interpolation spline models. In International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies: Applications, Trends and Opportunities, ICISCT 2019. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICISCT47635.2019.9011926> .
WWW.HUMOSCIENCE.COM

- [3] Hakimjon Zaynidinov, Sayfiddin Bakhromov, Bunyod Azimov, Sarvar Makhmudjanov. Comparative Analysis Spline Methods in Digital Processing of Signals // *Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal (ASTESJ)*, (Indexed by SCOPUS), <https://dx.doi.org/10.25046/aj0506180> , ISSN: 2415-6698, Vol. 5, No. 6, 1499-1510 (2020), www.astesj.com
- [4] Singh, M., Zaynidinov, H., Zaynutdinova, M., & Singh, D. (2019). Bi-cubic spline based temperature measurement in the thermal field for navigation and time system. *Journal of Applied Science and Engineering*, 22(3), 579–586.
[https://doi.org/10.6180/jase.201909_22\(3\).0019](https://doi.org/10.6180/jase.201909_22(3).0019)
- [5] Azimov B.R. Digital processing of signals using natural and local cubic splines // *Scientific and technical journal of Bukhara Institute of Engineering Technologies*. 2020, Bukhara. -B 125-132.Y. A. Üncü, T. Mercan, G. Sevim, and M. Canpolat, “Interpolation applications in diffuse optical tomography system,” 2018, doi: 10.1109/BIYOMUT.2017.8478855.
- [6] J.S. Lim, *Two-dimensional signal and image processing*, 1990.
- [7] V. Graffigna, C. Brunini, M. Gende, M. Hernández-Pajares, R. Galván, F. Oreiro, “Retrieving geophysical signals from GPS in the La Plata River region,” *GPS Solutions*, 23(3), 2019, doi:10.1007/s10291-019-0875-6.
- [8] X. Wang, Z. Luo, B. Zhong, Y. Wu, Z. Huang, H. Zhou, Q. Li, “Separation and recovery of geophysical signals based on the Kalman Filter with GRACE gravity data,” *Remote Sensing*, 11(4), 2019, doi:10.3390/rs11040393.
- [9] A.I. Grebennikov, “Isogeometric approximation of functions of one variable,” *USSR Computational Mathematics and Mathematical Physics*, 22(6), 1982, doi:10.1016/0041-5553(82)90095-7.
- [10] Kroizer, Y.C. Eldar, T. Routtenberg, “Modeling and recovery of graph signals and difference-based signals,” in *GlobalSIP 2019 - 7th IEEE Global Conference on Signal and Information Processing, Proceedings*, 2019, doi:10.1109/GlobalSIP45357.2019.8969536

[11] Azimov B.R. Significance of local interpolation cubic spline in digital processing of signals. Innovative solutions to engineering and technological problems in modern production is an international scientific conference. Bukhara 2019. - B. 533-535

[12] Azimov B.R. Construction of a local cubic spline for unequal intervals in the digital processing of signals // Collection of materials of the national scientific-practical conference on the topic "Prospects for the development of the quality of education and scientific research in the higher education system: problems and solutions". 2020. Namangan. - B. 8-10. M. Abduganiev, R. Azimov, and L. Muydinov, Digital Processing Algorithms of Biomedical Signals Using Cubic Base Splines, vol. 13741 LNCS. 2023. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-27199-1_3.

[13] Zaynidinov H.N., Azimov B.R., Abduganiyev M.M. - "Program for digital processing of medical images based on spline methods" copyright certificate DGU 2022 6051, 2022;

[14] Azimov B.R., Abduganiyev M.M. - "Analysis of local spline functions in digital processing of signals" - UzA, No. 01 (39), 2023.

https://uza.uz/uz/poss/signallarga-raqamli-ishlov-berishda-lokal-splayn-funksiyari-tahlili_445527